



Figure 2: Moran's I correlogram for LRS at Kimbe island (with associated standard deviations) before (A) and after (B) correcting for spatial autocorrelation with the Egs selected by the PCNM (see method). Moran's index was calculated at 4 distance classes, from 230m to 920m, with a distance lag of 230m. There is a significant and positive spatial autocorrelation at 230m and 460m and a significant negative spatial autocorrelation at 690m and 920m in LRS before correcting for spatial autocorrelation (A). Spatial autocorrelation was undetected in LRS after correcting with the PCs (B).